

PARENT'S ROLE AND ACHIEVEMENT OF THE CHILDREN WITH AUTISM IN SPECIAL SCHOOLS PAMEKASAN DISTRICT, EAST JAVA PROVINCE, INDONESIA

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Abstract

Parents' role was very important for the education of the children with autism. It is because the parents' attitude and behavior affect the achievement of the children with autism. One of the parents' role to improve the achievement of the children with autism is by giving the attention for the activities.

This research aims to find "The Correlation between parents' role and achievement of children autism". The subject of the research is the children with autism at school for children with special needs in Pamekasan District. This research uses correlation research by using Spearman rank method to find if there is a correlation between variables. Questionnaire and documentation techniques which are used to collect to the data.

Based on the data analysis, $r = 0,0179$. It is smaller than *rho* table. The result for the significant error for 5% is 0,738 and for 1% is 0,881. Therefore, *H₀* is accepted and *H_a* is rejected. The result of the data analysis shows that the correlation between *X* variable and *Y* variable was weak. Also, there was not trusted correlation between both variables. Based on the result of the research, it can be concluded that (1) The parents of children with autism in Pamekasan in active in the children's education, be able to cooperate with school well, and pay attention to the children either at school or home, (2) the achievement of the children with autism in Pamekasan is still low. It is proven by the result of the Students' report at school for special needs children in Pamekasan, (3) parent' role and the achievements' of the children with autism at school for special needs children in Pamekasan shows that there is not trusted correlation between both of them.

Keywords: Parents' role, achievement, children with autism.

Introduction

A family had important role for developing children in conducting basic forming of children's attitude, characteristics, moral, and education. In family environment, all parents' attitude and behavior really affected toward the children's development because father and mother were the real and the first educator so that the parents' attitude and behavior would be observed by the children either deliberately or not as experience which would influence the next education.

One of the parents' roles toward the education success was by giving attention especially to study activity at home and school. The parents' attention had great psychology influence toward the children's study activity. The parents' attention had positive relation to the children's study achievement at school.

Praweswari (1999:67-68) stated, "The parents' role was the parents' participation in giving good preparation for their children to reach the education success they were running in. The indicators of the parents' role were attention toward the children's lesson activity at school and emphasizing the importance of achieving the study achievement."

Many parents considered that after their children had been sent to the school the parents' right and duty to give education were over and all parents' responsibilities had turned to the teacher in the school, whether the children would be smart or not, would be nice boy with noble character or naughty. The parents, however, did not realize yet that there were many other factors which influenced the children's study achievement.

A study achievement was maximum result reached by someone after passing study process. The study achievement then depended on the study process quality in the class i.e. concerning with the roles of teacher, curriculum, fund, facility, infrastructure, and the children themselves. From many factors influencing the study achievement, social factor which consisted of family environment, school, society, and group had important role in reaching the study achievement. According to Gagne (in Dimiyati, 1999:10) study achievement was capability yielded from study activity in the form of skill, knowledge, attitude and a series of norms. The capability emerging was from (1) stimulus of environment, and (2) cognitive process performed by the children.

Every child deserved to get proper education including autism children. Not all autism children had under average IQ there were several autism children who had superior ability and extraordinary talent. It indicated that the autism children's ability could still be enhanced as optimum as possible. To enhance the autism children's ability required team work between school and parents. Sutadi (2003:155) stated that not all autism children had under average IQ. There were 35% autism children having above normal IQ while 65% were children with intelligence level under average.

Plaisted (in Jamaris, 2009:301) stated about 0,5%-10% of autism children with ASD indicated their extraordinary ability, start from ability in arranging puzzle with small pieces, memorizing in detail and very detail till other abilities and extraordinary talent. Many autism children had superior ability in perception and attention.

Autism was very complex syndrome which was signed by the characteristics of less ability of social interaction, communication, and behavior disturbance, and these symptoms had appeared before 3 years old. Because the disturbance was in the development center the autism children experienced complex development disorder which got impact to the development of the autism children's study achievement. Delpine (2009:53) stated, "Autism children had difficulty in study skills and new concepts. Although they were smart they would pretend to be disable children or *underachiever*, they had social problem. They got difficulty in having friends, playing, and communicating to others."

If it was not handled seriously it would emerge problem which would make the children get disturbance in study. Autism children with their disturbance often failed to reach their study achievement as the normal children who did not have disturbance in receiving and processing information. It required the parents' role because the children spent their time more at home with their parents so it was important for the parents to prepare themselves to be able to accompany and guide the autism children to be more optimal individual.

Autism children with disturbance often failed to reach the study achievement as the normal children who did not have disturbance in receiving and processing information. It required the parents' role because the children spent their time more at home with their parents so it was important for the parents to prepare themselves to be able to accompany and guide the autism children to be more optimal individual. Bonny (2003:175) states "Because of the nerve disorder the children were weak or had problem in one or several subject matters at school such as reading, writing, language, mathematics, social , or geography.

Based on the observation in special school of Pamekasan District, most of the parents' attitude indicated that the school became a storage place for children to enhance their children's ability and the parents gave little attention to the children development and rarely motivated their children at home. It was caused by less understanding about handling the autism children at home. The parents should be the motivator and should participate in enhancing the autism children's study achievement because the school without parent's role in education would not develop the children optimally.

Method

This research used non experiment kind with correlation arrangement and spearman rank method to know whether there was relationship among variables or not and the data collection method used questionnaire and documentation.

Result and discussion

Presenting data

The instrument tryout was done to know the validity and reliability of the data collector instrument which would be used in this research. The data collector instrument in this research was questionnaire. The steps, performed to know the level of validity and reliability, were as the following:

Validity

To know the validity level of a research instrument measurement it was used product moment formula and the steps performed were as the following:

Spreading the questionnaire of parents' role and reaching the autism children's study achievement to the respondents outside the research sample, 30 people. The respondents were the autism children's parents.

Making table containing column for question item and row containing respondent number.

Adding the score for each item.

Adding the whole score.

Counting each correlation using product moment formula.

Consulting the counting result to r table with significant level 5%.

Based on the steps, the next counted the items from 1 and so on with the steps as the following:

Making the qualification table of tryout result of parents' role and reaching the autism children's study achievement questionnaires.

Making the preparation table of counting validity questionnaire. Counting correlation item number 1 and so on suitable with product moment correlation.

From the data of correlation counting of parents' role and reaching the study achievement questionnaires it could be known that question number 1, 2, 3, 5, 9, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 21, 23, 25, 26, 27, 28, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37, 38, 39, 40, 41 were stated valid while question number 4, 6, 7, 8, 10, 11, 18, 19, 20, 22, 24, 29 were stated invalid. In this way, the valid questionnaires became a research instrument i.e. parents' role and reaching the study achievement of autism children questionnaires.

Reliability

To know the reliability level of a research instrument, it was used split two technique with spearman brown formula. The following was the table of counting preparation of parents' role and reaching the study achievement of autism children questionnaires.

From the reliability counting of parents' role and reaching the study achievement of autism children questionnaires it was obtained r counted 0,937 and it was consulted to r table of significant level 5% with $N = 30$ which had refusal limit H_0 (Null Hypothesis) 0,361. In this way, it could be known that r counted was greater than r table i.e. $0,937 > 0,361$ which meant the instrument was reliable.

After doing instrument tryout and reliability test and we knew that the instrument was valid and reliable it was done collecting data to the sample in SLB (Special School) at Pamekasan District.

Managing data

The data of autism children's parents in SDLB (Elementary Special School) Bugih Pamekasan, SLB (Special School) Asih Mulya Pamekasan, and SDLB (Elementary Special School) PGRI Pademawu Pamekasan became the research subject, the finding result in the field about the relationship of parent's role toward study achievement i.e. the children in the three schools of Pamekasan district to the rapport value of first semester in 2013-2014 school year could be checked to table 4.1 below.

Table 4.1 - The data of parents and autism children in special school (SLB) Pamekasan

No	Parents' name	Children's name	School
1	KA	MS	SDLB BUGIH Pamekasan
2	BG	AI	SDLB PGRI Pamekasan
3	HG	PT	SDLB PGRI Pamekasan
4	FR	RA	SDLB BUGIH Pamekasan
5	RD	AE	SLB Asih Mulya Pamekasan
6	BA	IL	SLB Asih Mulya Pamekasan
7	FH	IQ	SLB Asih Mulya Pamekasan
		MA	SLB Asih Mulya Pamekasan

The data of autism children's rapport value in special school (SLB) Pamekasan in semester I in 2014-2015 school years could then be seen in table 4.2 below:

Table 4.2 - The rapport average value of autism children class IV Semester I

No	Children's Name	Average Value	School Name
1	MS	64	SDLB BUGIH Pamekasan
2	AI	65	SDLB PGRI Pamekasan
3	PT	66	SDLB PGRI Pamekasan

4	RA	66	SDLB BUGIH Pamekasan
5	AE	64	SLB Asih Mulya Pamekasan
6	IL	64	SLB Asih Mulya Pamekasan
7	IQ	65	SLB Asih Mulya Pamekasan
8	MA	64	SLB Asih Mulya Pamekasan
Total Average			64,75

After listing the autism children's rapport value in special school (SLB) Pamekasan district, the next step was to list the result of parents' role questionnaire with reaching the study achievement of autism children in special school (SLB) Pamekasan district could be viewed to table 4.3 below:

Table 4.3 - The result data of parent's role questionnaire

No	Parents' name	Total
1	KA	98
2	BG	103
3	HG	95
4	FR	97
5	RD	106
6	BA	95
7	FH	93
8	FH	82
Total		769

The next was to list the result of parents' questionnaire and the result of autism children's rapport. The data of each parents and autism children in special school (SLB) Pamekasan district could be viewed in table 4.4 below:

Table 4.4 - The data of parents' questionnaire and autism children's rapport value in special school (SLB) Pamekasan

No	Parents' name	The result of parents' role questionnaire	Children's name	Rapport value
1	KA	98	MS	64
2	BG	103	AI	65
3	HG	95	PT	66
4	FR	97	RA	66
5	RD	106	AE	64
6	BA	95	IL	64
7	FH	93	IQ	65
8	FH	82	MA	64
Total		769	Total	64,75

Data Analysis

According to Sugiono (2010:245), he stated that Spearman correlation was to work with ordinal data or ranking, and free distributing. Because Spearman rank correlation worked with ordinal data so the data should be changed first from ordinal data to ranking form. To count the coefficient of spearman correlation required helper table as table 4.4 below.

After collecting data the next was presenting data suitable with the respondent's answer and the result of autism children's rapport. As the data collection method, the research purpose and the data analysis technique used was so the next steps in presenting data were as the following:

- Making table containing column for item number and row for subject number.
- Changing the respondent's answer suitable with scoring manual.
- Moving the rapport average value of autism children to the table provided.
- Moving the respondent's answer to the table provided.
- Summing the item answer obtained from each research subject.

Dealing with the data analysis the empiric data obtained from the research in special school (SLB) Pamekasan was presenting, the following was the data in the form of table.

*Table 4.4 - The preparation of counting Rank Spearman
 Correlation of parents' role (X₁) and study achievement (Y₁)*

No	(X1)	(Y1)	Ranking (X1)	Ranking (Y1)		
1	98	64	3	6,5	-3,5	12,25
2	103	65	2	3,5	-1,5	2,25
3	95	66	5,5	1,5	4	16
4	97	66	4	1,5	2,5	6,25
5	106	64	1	6,5	-5,5	30,25
6	95	64	5,5	6,5	-1	1
7	93	65	7	3,5	3,5	12,25
8	82	64	8	6,5	1,5	2,25
Total	-	-	-	-	-5	82,5

Then to prove the null hypothesis, there was not relationship between parents' role and autism children's study achievement in whole Pamekasan district, it was used Rank Spearman correlation. From the helper table had been obtained so.

The value of ρ table for $n = 8$ with error level 5% was 0,738 and 1% = 0,881. The result of rho counted was smaller than rho table either for error level 5% or 1% i.e. 0,0179. It meant that there was not real appropriateness and there was not relationship which could be trusted between study achievement and parents' role.

In this way, H_0 which stated there was not relationship between parents' role and autism children's study achievement was accepted, and H_a which stated there was relationship between parents' role and autism children's study achievement was refused. So, the conclusion was there was not relationship which could be trusted between parents' role and autism children's study achievement.

Discussion

In the development, autism children's ability was different with the normal generally. The autism children had development disturbance which had impact to their academic ability. Autism children had disturbance in receiving some material at school so that they required special treatment.

Bonny (175) stated "Autism children had study difficulty which processed and produced information. Study difficulty made the children weak or had problem in one or even several subject matters in the school such as reading, writing, language, mathematics, social, or geography."

From the result of research finding in the field it was known that there was not relationship which could be trusted between parents' role and reaching autism children's study achievement in special school (SLB) Pamekasan. The counting result between parents questionnaire and the children's rapport value was less of rho table either in error level 5% or 1% i.e. 0,0179. It proved that to enhance the autism children's ability was not only parent factor.

To enhance autism children's study achievement was not only from parents' role needed but also many factors influencing it, such as working together to enhance the ability the autism children had as teacher, parent, environment, etc. Beside that the children's internal factor also influenced toward the autism children's study achievement at school.

Baharudin (2012:19) stated that the factors influencing study achievement were classified into two categories, internal and external factors. Both factors affected each other in individual's study process so that it determined the quality of study result. An internal factor was the children's inner factor and an external factor was environment factor.

In performing the research in special school (SLB) Pamekasan it was known that not only parent factor but media and infrastructure factors could influence the children's study achievement as well. The treatment of autism children in special school (SLB) Pamekasan could still be said less, such as there was not special class for autism children, there was

not special teacher handling autism children, and lack of attention from government to increase the media and infrastructure in special school (SLB) Pamekasan.

Slameto (2003:27) stated that reaching the study achievement required adequate facility and infrastructure in the school so that the children could learn calmly. With sufficient facility and infrastructure in the school the children could calmly.

So, to enhance autism children's study achievement required working together. Not only parents' role but also fund factor, curriculum factor, facility and infrastructure factors, and the children's ability could enhance the study achievement. Beside that parents with knowledge about children treatment were very low. Most of autism children's parents in Pamekasan district were late to do early intervention.

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